

Computational analysis of the structure and stability of the tetrahedral intermediate in the peptide bond formation reaction in peptidyl transferase center

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Abstract : Peptide synthesis is an important biological reaction. Both concerted and stepwise mechanisms are proposed for the peptide synthesis in ribosome. The stepwise mechanism takes place through a tetrahedral intermediate. We analyzed the geometry, chirality and stabilizing factors of the intermediate using a combined quantum mechanical/semiempirical method based on a model of crystal structure. The comparison of the optimized geometry of the intermediate and transition state analog (DCSN) shows that in case of ribosomal peptide synthesis the intermediate should be tetrahedral with S-chirality. The chiral specificity of the intermediate arises from the relative position of the A-site substrate and the P-site substrate. The present computational study conclusively shows that the geometry of the carbonyl carbon atom of P-site amino acid is changed from a planer state (reactant) to another planer state (product) via a tetrahedral intermediate during the peptide bond formation in the ribosome. The tetrahedral intermediate is chiral and has S-chirality. The specificity of chiral structure of the intermediate arises from the relative position of the A-site substrate and the P-site substrate. The generation of the other isomer of the tetrahedral intermediate (R isomer) is impossible during the peptide biosynthesis in the ribosome. As the architecture of the PTC is such that P-site and A-site substrates are enclosed in specific locations, other positions of the substrates are impossible. Consequently the nucleophilic attack by the α -amino group of A-site substrate from the two faces of the carbonyl carbon atom of P-site substrate is impossible. As a result only one isomer of the tetrahedral intermediate is possible during the ribosomal peptide synthesis which is stabilized via intra as well as intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions. The U2620 plays an important role in the stabilization of the geometry of the intermediate. This study is the first computational analysis of the structure and stabilization of the tetrahedral intermediate during the stepwise pathway of peptide synthesis.

Keywords : Tetrahedral intermediate, chirality, peptide bond formation, ribosome, peptidyl transferase center.

Introduction

Proteins are the most versatile molecules in living systems. Several different functions are performed by proteins such as catalysis, transport and storage of other molecules (such as oxygen), provide mechanical support and immune protection, and transmit nerve impulses. Proteins are synthesized through a sequence of steps and involve a number of macromolecules such as aminoacyl-tRNA synthetase and ribosome. The first step of protein synthesis is amino acid activation which is followed by initiation, elongation, termination and release as well as folding and post translational process. All these steps are subjects of intensive research over years^{1,2}. The nascent polypeptide chain length grows by covalent attachment of successive amino acids in the elongation step. The reac-

tion takes place in the active site of ribosome known as peptidyl transferase center (PTC). In this process, the nucleophilic α -amino group of the aminoacyl-tRNA at A-site makes a nucleophilic attack at the electrophilic carbonyl carbon atom of the ester bond of the peptidyl-tRNA at P-site and forms a tetrahedral intermediate, which subsequently generates the peptide bond. Both concerted and stepwise mechanisms are proposed for the peptide synthesis. Two mechanisms are competitive and are studied in detail using experiment and computational methods³⁻¹². The stepwise mechanism takes place through a tetrahedral intermediate. Although the transition states of the reaction are studied using computational methods, the understanding of the stability and interactions of the tetrahedral intermediate is limited⁷⁻⁹. The intermediate is

proposed to be chiral as well as zwitterionic^{1,2}. However, to the best of our knowledge, detailed quantum mechanical analysis of the structure and interaction of the tetrahedral intermediate is unavailable. Since both the concerted and stepwise mechanisms are competitive and it is yet to decide about the relative importance of one mechanism over the other, it is important to understand the features of the intermediate in detail which is a key factor for the stepwise path.

The schematic representation of the stepwise mechanism of peptide bond formation (excluding the geometry of transition state) is shown in the Fig. 1. A new chiral center (in addition to the chiral center of the α -carbon of each amino acid) is generated during the peptide bond formation within the structure of the tetrahedral intermediate (shown as C* in Fig. 1). The center converts to an achiral one once the electron density over the oxyanion atom shifts to form a double bond with the C* carbon atom (shown in Fig. 1), the bond between the 3' oxygen of P-site tRNA and C* breaks, a hydrogen attached with

the outcome of attacks on two faces are not same. The same is valid for peptide synthesis reaction. Consequently, the possibility of the formation of both R and S isomers of the tetrahedral intermediate exists in principle.

The influence of chirality in a biochemical reaction is a subject of tremendous interest due to its fundamental and technological importance. Proteins are made exclusively by L-amino acid. Though the D-amino acids are present in different organisms why they would be completely excluded during peptide synthesis in most organisms is unclear⁶. The possibility that the interaction of D-amino acid with L-amino acid during the possible formation of peptide bond between such enantiomeric species is energetically unfavorable is explored^{13,14}. During the ribosomal peptide synthesis the 3' end of A-site tRNA (containing the nucleophilic α -amino group) arrives at the P-site tRNA (where the nucleophilic α -amino group of A-site substrate attack) by a process of mutual rotation between them. The computational study shows that the

Fig. 1. The schematic representation of the reactant, intermediate and product state of the peptide bond formation reaction.

the amino group moves as a proton (that is without electron pair) to the 3' oxygen of P-site tRNA and simultaneously electron associated with the hydrogen atom of the positively charged amino group of A-site tRNA is moved to the nitrogen atom. The stereochemistry of nascent chiral center via the nucleophilic addition reaction in a carbonyl carbon atom depends on the relative position of the attacking nucleophile with respect to the electrophilic center. The attacking nucleophile can approach towards carbonyl carbon atom having planar geometry, from two opposite sides or faces of the carbonyl group. Except symmetric ketones, a racemic product results as

orientational space during this rotatory motion is favorable for the L-amino acid and highly unfavorable for the D-amino acid^{13,14}. The study shows that the chiral discrimination plays an important role in the peptide synthesis. The role of the chirality of sugar ring also analyzed¹¹. Change in the chirality of the sugar ring alters the reaction rate by several orders. However, to the best of our knowledge, no electronic structure based study about the chirality of the tetrahedral intermediate has been carried out.

The crystal structure of the ribosome of *Haloarcula marismortui* (Hma) complexed with different transition state analogs are studied to analyze different features of

the tetrahedral intermediate⁷⁻⁹. The experimental study shows that when the mixture of the two diastereomers of intermediate (transition state analog) was soaked into the ribosome, only the S isomer was present in the electron density maps. This observation suggests peptide synthesis proceeds through a tetrahedral intermediate of S configuration. The study further indicated that the oxyanion of the intermediate interacts with a solvent water molecule which is anchored by the A2637 and U2619 of PTC. The α -amino group of the A-site substrate (positively charged) of the intermediate interacts with the N3 atom of nucleotide A2486 and the 2' hydroxyl group of A76 of P-site substrate. The structural analysis suggests that the zwitterionic tetrahedral intermediate is stabilized by various hydrogen bonding interactions and no metal ion(s) is involved in the stabilization of the geometry of the intermediate⁸. Another study suggests that the nucleotide U2620 may move to stabilize the oxyanion of zwitterionic intermediate during the ribosomal peptide synthesis⁷. The computational study also shows that the tetrahedral intermediate with S configuration is more preferred for the non-ribosomal peptide bond formation¹².

It is an important question that why the configuration of the tetrahedral intermediate is specifically S enantiomeric. Is it completely determined by the architecture of PTC or by the preference of the rotatory path of the two terminals? Further question is that once S chirality is generated, how the stability of the corresponding structure compares with that of the corresponding R enantiomer (since, both enantiomeric forms are equally probable from the point of view of isolated enantiomeric forms). In particular, the question is that which interactions between PTC and terminals favor S enantiomer over the R enantiomer. The present paper is aimed to understand these questions. The available crystal structures of the 50S ribosomal subunit of *Haloarcula marismortui*⁷ gives the molecular details of the architecture of PTC as well as relative arrangement of the reactant substrate molecules which is used to understand the foregoing questions. Two level ONIOM (HF/3-21G*:PM3) method is used. The optimized geometry of the model structure of the tetrahedral intermediate as computed in the present work is compared with the geometry of the transition state analog bound in the active site of ribosome⁸. The reason of the chiral specificity of the tetrahedral intermediate is also

explored. The factors which are involved in the stabilization of the tetrahedral intermediate are studied. The computational details are presented in the next section.

Method and calculation :

The crystal structure of the CCA-Phe-caproic acid-biotin bound simultaneously at half-occupancy to both the A-site and P-site of the 50S ribosomal subunit of *Haloarcula marismortui* (1Q86.pdb)⁷ is used to generate the model structure of the reactant, intermediate and product. The crystal structure (A- and P-site substrate bound state) corresponds to the reactant state of the peptide synthesis. The relative separation between the α -amino group of A-site substrate (which is supposed to attack) and the carbonyl carbon atom of the ester bond of P-site substrate is 2.63 Å in the crystalline state. Their relative position and orientation is suitable for the nucleophilic attack of the former to the latter. Using this crystal structure a model of the reactant state, intermediate state as well as product state is generated. The corresponding models are denoted by Model_{Reactant}, Model_{Intermediate} and Model_{Product}, respectively.

The models include two substrate amino acids (phenylalanine molecules) which are bound with the CCA terminal of A-site and P-site tRNA and take part in the reaction as well as two sugar rings of the respective tRNAs (which connect the amino acid and tRNA). The adenine bases (A76) at the C₁ position of the respective sugar ring is replaced by a hydrogen atom. The C_{5'} oxygen atom is also replaced by the hydrogen atom as these parts of A76 nucleotide are far from the reaction center. The model also includes two bases of two nucleotides A2486 and U2620 which are in close proximity to the reaction center and expected to play a role in the reaction path. The model contains 103 atoms.

Two level ONIOM (HF/3-21G*:PM3) method is used to optimize the model structures. The combined quantum mechanical/molecular mechanical approach is extensively applied to larger systems¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Optimization of macromolecular system is relatively faster with the multilevel hybrid method that includes quantum and molecular mechanics, such as multilayered ONIOM model (abbreviation of the title "*our n-layered integrated molecular orbital and molecular mechanics*", as used by the developers)¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The major approximations in theoretic-

cal treatments of large systems are two-fold such as the use of smaller models and use of lower level of calculation. Small models exclude the electronic and steric effects from the remaining part of the large molecule and the lower level calculation excludes correlation effects. Thus, in a three-layered ONIOM model, the energy of a large system calculated using theory at high level with its real structure (High level, Real system) is approximated energy as

$$\begin{aligned} E(\text{High level, Real system}) \\ = E(\text{High level, Small model}) \\ + \Delta E(\text{High level, Intermediate model} \leftarrow \text{Small model}) \\ + \Delta E(\text{High level,} \\ \text{Real system} \leftarrow \text{Intermediate model}) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Here, $\Delta E(\text{High level, Intermediate model} \leftarrow \text{Small model})$ and $E(\text{High level, Real} \leftarrow \text{Intermediate model})$ accounts for the differences in energy due to the small model and intermediate model with that of the real model. In ONIOM scheme, these two quantities are approximated as :

$$\begin{aligned} E(\text{High level, Intermediate model} \leftarrow \text{Small model}) \\ \approx \Delta E(\text{Medium level, Intermediate model} \leftarrow \text{Small model}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E(\text{High level, Real system} \leftarrow \text{Intermediate model}) \\ \approx \Delta E(\text{Low level, Real system} \leftarrow \text{Intermediate model}) \end{aligned}$$

Assuming that the approximations give correct energy differences, eq. (1) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} E(\text{High level, Real system}) \\ = E(\text{High level, Small model}) \\ + \Delta E(\text{Medium level, Intermediate model} \leftarrow \text{Small model}) \\ + \Delta E(\text{Low level, Real system} \leftarrow \text{Intermediate model}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Eq. (2) can be explicitly written as,

$$\begin{aligned} E(\text{High level, Real system}) \\ = E(\text{High level, Small model}) + E(\text{Medium level, Intermediate model}) \\ + E(\text{Low level, Real system}) - E(\text{Medium level, Small model}) \\ - E(\text{Low level, Intermediate model}) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

It is important to partition the system into different levels with care. In the model, electronic structure of few groups such as carboxylic acid group and amino group changes due to bond formation and bond breaking. It is necessary to consider the atoms of these groups at high

level. Few other groups are nonbonded with the reactants but involved in the hydrogen bonding or charge stabilization and are also considered at high level. The atoms related to these groups such as the carboxylic acid group, amino group and chiral center of two phenylalanine molecules along with the two bases (A2486 and U2620) are considered as high level in the present model. The 2' OH of P-site sugar ring is also considered as high level as this group is suggested to be involved in the hydrogen bonding with the amino group of the A-site substrate. Remaining all atoms is considered at low level and semi-empirical method is applied for them. The optimized geometry of the $\text{Model}_{\text{Reactant}}$, $\text{Model}_{\text{Intermediate}}$ and $\text{Model}_{\text{Product}}$ are shown in the Fig. 2(a-c).

Fig. 2. Optimized geometry of the (a) $\text{Model}_{\text{Reactant}}$, (b) $\text{Model}_{\text{Intermediate}}$ and (c) $\text{Model}_{\text{Product}}$ using two level ONIOM (HF/3-21G*:PM3) method. For details, see text

In order to understand how the geometry and the structural parameters are changed during the reaction we compare different geometrical parameters of the optimized Model_{Reactant}, Model_{Intermediate} and Model_{Product}, respectively. The optimized geometry of the Model_{Intermediate} is compared with the transition state analog DCSN bound in the active site of ribosomal subunit as shown in the Fig. 3(a) and 3(b), respectively. The chirality of the newly generated tetrahedral center is also analyzed and com-

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. Optimized geometry of the (a) Model_{Intermediate} and (b) transition state analog (DCSN)⁸ representing the chiral center of the tetrahedral intermediate during the peptide bond formation in ribosome. For details, see text.

pared with the transition state analog. The factors which are involved in the intermediate stabilization are analyzed. In order to understand the reason of the chiral specificity of tetrahedral intermediate the relative position of the P-

site tRNA and A-site tRNA in the active site of ribosome is investigated. The corresponding geometries of the active site of ribosome are shown in the Fig. 4(a) and 4(b). Gaussian 03 suite of programs¹⁸ is used for all calculations. The results are described in the following section.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. The active site of 50S ribosomal subunit of *Haloarcula marismortui* (1Q86.pdb)⁷ (a) complexed with the CCA-Phe-caproic acid-biotin bound simultaneously at half-occupancy to both the A-site and P-site and (b) showing the exit tunnel at P-site for the nascent protein chain.

Results and discussion

The optimized geometry of the Model_{Reactant}, Model_{Intermediate} and Model_{Product} are shown in the Fig. 2(a-c). The result shows that the geometry of the carbonyl carbon atom of P-site amino acid is changed from a planar state to another planar state via a tetrahedral intermediate. This can be noted from the comparison of the

bond angles and distances around the carbonyl carbon atom in the optimized geometries of the reactant, intermediate and product state. The angle (chiral carbon atom of P-site substrate amino acid, Phe)C–C(carbonyl carbon of P-site substrate amino acid, Phe)–O(carbonyl oxygen P-site substrate amino acid, Phe) is changing from 126.35° (reactant) to 121.58° (product) via 116.71° (intermediate). While the separation between carbonyl carbon atom and the carbonyl oxygen atom of P-site substrate amino acid (Phe) (C---O separation) changes from 1.20 Å (reactant state) to 1.23 Å (product state) via 1.28 Å (intermediate state). The computed bond angles and bond distances in the reactant, intermediate and product confirm the view that the geometry of the carbonyl carbon atom changes from one planar state to another planar state via tetrahedral intermediate. The Mulliken population analysis shows that the electron density over the carbonyl oxygen atom of the P-site substrate amino acid, Phe is greater in intermediate state than either reactant or product state. This indicates that the optimized geometry is indeed an oxyanion state.

The optimized geometry of the Model_{Intermediate} and transition state analog (DCSN) bound in the active site of ribosomal subunit is shown in the Fig. 3(a) and 3(b), respectively. The selected structural parameters of the respective geometries are listed in the Tables 1A and 1B, respectively. The average bond angle between the atoms attached with the tetrahedral carbon atom of the intermediate in optimized Model_{Intermediate} is 109.14° and for the transition state analog (DCSN) the average bond angle between the atoms attached with the phosphorus atom (mimic the tetrahedral carbon atom of the intermediate)

is 109.44°. This indicates that the geometry of the optimized intermediate is tetrahedral and it is similar with the geometry of the transition state analog (DCSN). The relative orientation of the groups or substituents attached with the chiral center C* (generated during the reaction) for the optimized model of intermediate are shown in the Fig. 3(a). The structures compares well with that of the DCSN. This result confirms that the spatial arrangement of the groups around the C* in the intermediate matches with that of the analogous P atom in the transition state analog (DCSN). The present computational study confirms that the chirality of the tetrahedral intermediate should have S chirality. The specific S chirality of the tetrahedral intermediate arises from the confined relative position of the substrate molecules. The particular configuration of the tetrahedral intermediate indicates that the face of the carbonyl carbon atom through which the nucleophilic attack by the α -amino group of the aminoacyl-tRNA at A-site takes place, must be precise. The relative position of the A-site substrate and P-site substrate does not permit the attack of the former to later from the opposite face of the later.

It is asked in the introduction that why the configuration of the tetrahedral intermediate is specifically S enantiomeric and whether the architecture of PTC or the preference of the rotatory path of the two terminals is the crucial factor for the specificity. The crystal structure of PTC shows that it is impossible for the A-terminal to attack the P-terminal in a way such that the R enantiomer could be generated¹⁹ as shown in the Fig. 4(a). The location of the P-terminal is specific and close to the exit tunnel so that the growing polypeptide chain can elongate

Table 1A. Bond lengths between the C* and the four groups attached in the optimized geometry of the tetrahedral intermediate (Model_{Intermediate}) and the bond lengths between the P* and the four groups attached in the transition state analog (DCSN)

Optimized tetrahedral intermediate (Model _{Intermediate})			DCSN analogue of the tetrahedral intermediate		
Atom 1 involved in the bond	Atom 2 involved in the bond	Separation in the optimized Model _{Intermediate} (Å)	Atom 1 involved in the bond	Atom 2 involved in the bond	Separation in the transition state analog
C* of tetrahedral carbon atom	Oxygen of oxyanion	1.28	Central chiral phosphorus atom (P*) of the analog	Sulfur of the analogue	2.00
C* of tetrahedral carbon atom	Nitrogen atom of the amine group	1.62	Central chiral phosphorus atom (P*) of the analog	Nitrogen atom of the analogue	1.67
C* of tetrahedral carbon atom	3' O of P-site ribiose	1.46	Central chiral phosphorus atom (P*) of the analog	3' O of P-site ribiose	1.60
C* of tetrahedral carbon atom	Chiral center of P-site amino acid	1.54	Central chiral phosphorus atom (P*) of the analog	Carbon of ethanoic acid	1.68

Table 1B. Bond angles between the C* and the four groups attached in the optimized geometry of the tetrahedral intermediate (Model_{Intermediate}) and the bond angles between the P* and the four groups attached in the transition state analog (DCSN)

Optimized tetrahedral intermediate (Model _{Intermediate})		DCSN analogue of the tetrahedral intermediate				
Atom 1 involved in the bond angle	Atom 2 involved in the bond angle	Atom 3 involved in the bond angle	Atom 1 involved in the bond angle	Atom 2 involved in the bond angle	Atom 3 involved in the bond angle	Angle in the transition state analog (degree)
Oxygen of oxyanion	C* of tetrahedral carbon atom	Nitrogen atom of the amino group	Sulfur of the analogue	Central chiral phosphorus atom (P*) of the analog	Nitrogen atom of the amino group	110.58
Oxygen of oxyanion	C* of tetrahedral carbon atom	3' O of P-site ribose	Sulfur of the analogue	Central chiral phosphorus atom (P*) of the analog	3' O of P-site ribose	113.96
Oxygen of oxyanion	C* of tetrahedral carbon atom	Chiral center of P-site amino acid	Sulfur of the analogue	Central chiral phosphorus atom (P*) of the analog	Carbon of ethanoic acid	116.71
Nitrogen atom of the amino group	C* of tetrahedral carbon atom	3' O of P-site ribose	Nitrogen atom of the amino group	Central chiral phosphorus atom (P*) of the analog	3' O of P-site ribose	96.59
Nitrogen atom of the amino group	C* of tetrahedral carbon atom	Chiral center of P-site amino acid	Nitrogen atom of the amino group	Central chiral phosphorus atom (P*) of the analog	Carbon of ethanoic acid	108.39
3' O of P-site ribose	C* of tetrahedral carbon atom	Chiral center of P-site amino acid	3' O of P-site ribose	Central chiral phosphorus atom (P*) of the analog	Carbon of ethanoic acid	108.64

without hindrance. This is shown in Fig. 4(b). As the spatial arrangement of the A-site and P-site substrate will be changed in the intermediate with R chirality the hydrogen bonds involved in the stabilization of the intermediate state would become nonexistent in the R enantiomeric structure. However, due to the lack of any experimentally available structure of the intermediate, these propositions need to be verified. Consequently, while the structure of the PTC determines the chirality of the S enantiomer of the tetrahedral intermediate, the intermediate is stabilized by a number of hydrogen bonds which are not possible in R enantiomer.

Further question asked is that once S chirality is generated, how the stability of the corresponding structure compares with that of the corresponding R enantiomer and which interactions between PTC and terminals favor S enantiomer over the R enantiomer. The computed geometry of the intermediate provides clear answer to these questions. The tetrahedral intermediate is stabilized via intra as well as intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions which was proposed from crystal structure of analogues^{7,8} and is noted in the case of intermediate optimized in the present calculation (Fig. 5). The α -amino

group of the A-site substrate is stabilized by an intramolecular hydrogen bond between hydrogen attached with α -amino group of the A-site substrate and the 2' OH group of the sugar ring of P-site tRNA. Intermolecular hydrogen bonding is also noted between another hydrogen atom attached with the α -amino group of the A-site substrate and the N3 atom of the nucleotide A2486 constituting the PTC. The oxyanion attached with the chiral center of the tetrahedral intermediate also forms hydrogen bond with the U2620 which is a part of PTC. This interaction is very important as the electron density over the oxyanion in the intermediate state is stabilized via this interaction. The earlier study also shows that the U2620 is involved in the chiral discrimination¹⁴. The present study illustrates that the nucleotide U2620 not only involved in the chiral discrimination but also plays a role in the stabilization of the intermediate.

Conclusion :

The present computational study conclusively shows that the geometry of the carbonyl carbon atom of P-site amino acid is changed from a planar state (reactant) to another planar state (product) via a tetrahedral intermediate during the peptide bond formation in the ribosome.

Fig. 5. Different intra and intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions as observed in the optimized geometry of the intermediate and are shown by the dotted line. These interactions are involved in the intermediate stabilization and are discussed in the text.

The tetrahedral intermediate is chiral and has S chirality. The specificity of chiral structure of the intermediate arises from the relative position of the A-site substrate and the P-site substrate. The generation of the other isomer of the tetrahedral intermediate (R isomer) is impossible during the peptide biosynthesis in the ribosome. As the PTC has architecture which is designed for the P-site and A-site substrates to locate them in specific positions, other possible positions of the substrates are impossible. Consequently the nucleophilic attack by the α -amino group of A-site substrate from the two faces of the carbonyl carbon atom of P-site substrate is impossible. As a result only one isomer of the tetrahedral intermediate is possible during the ribosomal peptide synthesis which is stabilized via intra as well as intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions. The U2620 plays an important role in the stabilization of the geometry of the intermediate. This study is the first computational analysis of the structure and stabilization of the tetrahedral intermediate during the stepwise pathway of peptide synthesis.

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